

Learn2Reg: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Learn2Reg

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

Learn2Reg

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Biomedical image registration is ubiquitously used in science and hospitals, yet recent research developments do not directly translate into improved clinical workflows. Learn2Reg has consistently worked to bridge this gap by establishing comprehensive tasks tailored to address critical clinical needs, while ensuring fair independent evaluation.

Recent advances in deep learning have shifted the research focus of MICCAI toward segmentation and classification, often sidelining the equally critical domain of image registration. Learn2Reg 2026 aims to encourage research in this area, emphasizing the unique challenges inherent to the ill-posed nature of registration problems and the need for domain-specific adaptations of learning techniques. The initiative also aims to strengthen connections between research groups working on complementary challenges, encouraging collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Building on the framework and insights established in previous editions, Learn2Reg 2026 will continue advancing the field of image registration with a focus on two subtasks driven by urgent clinical needs in therapy planning and assessment. The first subtask, PSMAReg, will promote the development of advanced registration methods for cancer therapy response assessment and optimization, with a particular emphasis on aligning pre-therapy and post-therapy whole-body PSMA PET/CT scans. In current clinical practice, such sequential registrations often rely on suboptimal workflows that involve rigid or weakly deformable registration with substantial manual intervention. The second subtask, Learn2Breath, will target large-deformation lung image registration, motivated by clinically relevant challenges in modeling and quantifying structural changes associated with obstructive pulmonary disease. Differently from the existing lung image registration challenges, the Learn2Breath challenge will focus specifically on chest computed tomography scans with large change in volumes, with the goal of encouraging new methods focusing particularly on this challenging but clinically relevant subset. Together, these subtasks are designed to stimulate methodological innovation while maintaining a clear pathway toward clinical

impact. Importantly, both subtasks are new contributions to Learn2Reg this year demonstrating the continued innovation of the organizing team.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Registration, Deformable, PET, CT, Oncology, Multimodal, COPD

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The novelty of Learn2Reg 2026 lies in its deliberate focus on two clinically important yet unresolved problems in biomedical image registration: 1) whole-body PET/CT registration (PSMAReg) and 2) large-deformation lung registration in a COPD cohort (Learn2Breath). These subtasks target distinct and challenging scenarios, namely pre- and post-therapy whole-body therapeutic PET/CT registration and large-deformation lung registration in a complex patient group.

Despite the significant progress achieved in previous Learn2Reg editions, this will be the first public computational challenge to explicitly address whole-body PET/CT registration in a cancer therapy setting. In current clinical and dosimetry workflows, such registrations still largely rely on rigid or manually refined approaches. This gap persists in part because nuclear medicine imaging has remained underrepresented within the MICCAI community, reflecting both the relative scarcity of large-scale PET datasets and the inherent complexity of molecular imaging. As a consequence, whole-body PET/CT registration remains insufficiently explored despite posing substantial technical challenges, including large patient repositioning differences between therapy time points, the limited spatial resolution and contrast of PET images for reliable feature identification, and the critical requirement to preserve quantitative PET-derived biomarkers, such as standardized uptake values (SUVs), so that clinically meaningful information is not altered by the registration process.

To ensure strong clinical relevance and community engagement, Learn2Reg 2026 is organized in close collaboration with the SNMMI Physics, Instrumentation, and Data Sciences Council (PIDSC). This collaboration helps align the challenge design, evaluation criteria, and benchmarking goals with real-world needs in nuclear medicine, radiopharmaceutical therapy, and patient-specific dosimetry, further strengthening the translational impact of the proposed challenge.

In parallel, while lung registration has been explored in earlier editions of Learn2Reg, the Learn2Breath subtask will shift the emphasis toward large deformations that arise from disease progression and respiratory mechanics, capturing clinically realistic anatomical changes that remain insufficiently handled by existing approaches. This is particularly true for detecting early stage lung disease, where deformation is large but biomechanical tissue changes are subtle and require more accurate image registration for understanding lung motion.

Building on the legacy of prior Learn2Reg challenges, both subtasks are expected to drive methodological advances in deformable image registration and to have a lasting impact on the broader medical imaging and

clinical research communities.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

PSMAReg: This task aims to address deformable registration of sequential whole-body PSMA PET/CT scans acquired before and after cancer therapy, a critical yet underdeveloped component of prostate cancer management. In current clinical and dosimetric workflows, such registrations are often limited to rigid or manually refined approaches, which are insufficient to account for large patient repositioning, anatomical changes, and therapy-related effects across time points. This task targets the unique challenges of molecular imaging-based registration, where PET images suffer from low spatial resolution, noise, and heterogeneous tracer uptake, and the accompanying low-dose CT, primarily acquired for attenuation correction, provides limited anatomical detail. In addition, registration methods must preserve quantitative PET-derived biomarkers to avoid altering clinically meaningful measures.

The methods developed through PSMAReg are expected to support several key clinical applications:

1. **Patient-Specific Dosimetry and Therapy Planning:** Accurate whole-body registration enables reliable voxel-wise dose accumulation across sequential scans across time points, improving estimation of dose to tumors and dose-limiting organs and supporting therapy optimization in radiopharmaceutical and radiation therapies.
2. **Therapy Response Assessment:** Robust alignment across time points facilitates consistent evaluation of PSMA-avid lesions and normal organs, allowing reliable assessment of treatment response while preserving quantitative PET biomarker measures such as standard uptake values, metabolic tumor volume, and total lesion glycolysis.
3. **Clinical Workflow Standardization:** By providing a public benchmark for whole-body PSMA PET/CT registration, PSMAReg promotes the development of robust, clinically applicable methods that reduce reliance on manual refinement and improve reproducibility across institutions.

Learn2Breath: Deformable image registration (DIR) of the inspiratory and expiratory chest CT scans has been used to quantify spatial biomechanical properties of the lung. Biomarkers derived through DIR have been associated with lung function decline, reduced exercise capacity, increased risk of hospitalizations and all-cause mortality. Despite their success in characterizing severe lung disease, most biomarkers are not sensitive enough to capture early lung disease, where changes are subtle and harder to capture. Such cases, while clinically relevant for improving outcomes, are hard to detect. This challenge has been designed to directly address this need i.e., characterize large deformations in early disease and distinguish them from normal biomechanics.

The methods developed would help in the following different ways:

1. **Improved Characterizing of Lung Motion:** By specifically improving DIR of the lungs under large deformation, the new methods will enable extraction of spatial biomarkers more accurately reflective of lung function.
2. **Early Obstructive Lung Disease:** Unlike most existing biomarkers that are more sensitive to severe disease,

more accurate DIR-based biomarkers will be able to potentially identify early-stage disease which could help early intervention, treatment planning, and lifestyle changes.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

To be determined

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

We request a half-day slot to accommodate the structure and scope of the Learn2Reg challenge. For each subtask, the top 10 teams on the validation leaderboard are traditionally invited to present short talks describing their methods before the final test-phase rankings are revealed. This format has proven effective in promoting transparency, methodological diversity, and meaningful technical discussion among participants and attendees.

In addition, the challenge program includes an invited keynote lecture to provide broader scientific and clinical context. For example, at Learn2Reg 2025, we invited Prof. Mirabela Rusu from Stanford University, who delivered a keynote talk that was very well received by the community. Continuing this format in 2026 will further enhance the educational and scientific value of the event.

Given the number of anticipated participating teams, the inclusion of multiple subtasks, the presentation of top-ranked methods, and the invited keynote, a longer session is necessary to ensure sufficient time for technical presentations, discussion, and engagement without compromising the depth or quality of the program.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Based on the organizing team's experience with the Learn2Reg community over the past two years, we expect a similar or larger number of participants than last year. Specifically, the ReMIND2Reg subtask had 14 teams compete in Daejeon (MICCAI 2025), while the LUMIR challenge had 20 teams involved in the final event.

For reference, please see the 2023 Learn2Reg summary paper (<https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2022.3213983>), which had more than 50 contributors and the 2024 Learn2Reg summary paper (<https://doi.org/10.59275/j.melba.2025-gc8c>) similarly attracted over 50 contributors. These numbers highlight the continued growth and broad participation of the Learn2Reg initiative across the years.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Following previous Learn2Reg challenge editions, participants must submit a short description of their methods via arXiv, based on their leaderboard results, to be eligible for test phase participation. Selected participants who contribute to the test phase will later (after the challenge concludes) be invited to submit a more detailed method description. These submissions will be compiled into the Learn2Reg proceedings, which may be published as an arXiv collection or included in open-access journals such as MELBA.

For each task, we plan to write a joint manuscript with the participants summarizing the findings of both subtasks in Learn2Reg 2026. The organizing team has a proven record of getting Learn2Reg results published including:

1. Hering, Alessa, et al. "Learn2Reg: comprehensive multi-task medical image registration challenge, dataset and evaluation in the era of deep learning." *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 42.3 (2022): 697-712.
2. Hansen, Lasse, et al. "Learn2Reg 2024: New Benchmark Datasets Driving Progress on New Challenges." *Machine Learning for Biomedical Imaging* 3.December 2025 issue (2025): 775-791.
3. Chen, Junyu, et al. "Beyond the LUMIR challenge: The pathway to foundational registration models." arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.24160 (2025).
4. Dorent, Reuben, et al. "The Brain Resection Multimodal Image Registration (ReMIND2Reg) 2025 Challenge." arXiv preprint arXiv:2508.09649 (2025).

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Learn2Reg is an off-site challenge, and we will make use of the grand-challenge.org website to host the challenge, evaluation engine, and leaderboards.

On the day of the challenge, a projector, a computer, and two microphones will be needed for the presentations

of the winning methods

TASK 1: PSMAReg: Pre-Therapy and Follow-Up Whole-Body PSMA PET/CT Registration

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Prostate cancer is one of the most common cancers among men in the United States and is highly prone to metastatic spread. Prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA) PET has demonstrated high sensitivity for detecting metastatic prostate cancer, particularly in settings where anatomical imaging modalities such as CT show limited sensitivity. As a result, PSMA PET has become increasingly important in a range of clinical applications, including patient-specific dosimetry planning for cancer therapies such as external beam radiation therapy and radiopharmaceutical therapy, as well as the longitudinal assessment of treatment response.

Across these applications, accurate alignment of pre-therapy and follow-up PSMA PET/CT scans is critical. Reliable registration enables clinicians, including radiation oncologists and nuclear medicine physicians, to quantify the spatial and temporal accumulation of delivered dose within both tumor targets and dose-limiting normal organs. This information is essential for estimating therapeutic efficacy, evaluating organ tolerance, and guiding treatment optimization over time. By explicitly addressing the technical challenges associated with whole-body PSMA PET/CT registration in a therapeutic setting, this challenge aims to promote the development of robust, clinically applicable registration methods with direct impact on personalized therapy planning and response assessment.

Despite its clinical importance, pre-therapy and follow-up scans of the same patient often exhibit substantial differences in patient positioning, bed placement, and disease-related anatomical changes, encompassing both rigid and non-rigid deformations. In current clinical practice, registration of such sequential scans largely relies on rigid registration or conventional optimization-based methods with manual refinement, both of which are prone to error in this setting. Prior studies have shown that misregistration between sequential scans can lead to significant errors in dose estimation, thereby limiting therapeutic effectiveness and potentially compromising patient outcomes. Consequently, the development of registration methods specifically tailored to this application remains scarce.

This task, hosted as part of Learn2Reg 2026, will be the first public computational challenge to explicitly focus on this underexplored yet clinically critical problem. The proposed PSMAReg task will leverage whole-body PSMA PET/CT data from the autoPET challenge, comprising 597 scans from 378 patients, including 164 patients with two or more longitudinal follow-up scans, for training and validation. The test set will consist of 262 PSMA PET/CT scans acquired internally at Johns Hopkins University from 131 patients using similar whole-body acquisition protocols. For training and validation, manually annotated lesion masks on PET and automatically segmented organs on low-dose CT will be provided. For testing, evaluation labels will include manually annotated lesions and PSMA-avid organs on PET, along with automatically labeled organs on CT.

To ensure strong clinical relevance and alignment with real-world nuclear medicine practice, PSMAReg is organized in close collaboration with the SNMMI Physics, Instrumentation, and Data Sciences Council (PIDSC*). This dataset design intentionally evaluates robustness to distributional shift between the autoPET and Johns Hopkins cohorts, closely reflecting realistic clinical deployment scenarios. Overall, this challenge aims to catalyze methodological advances in whole-body PSMA PET/CT registration while fostering clinically grounded solutions that can be translated into routine therapy planning, dosimetry, and response assessment.

*SNMMI PIDSC website: <https://snmmi.org/Web/About/About-SNMMI/Councils/Physics--Instrumentation-and-Data-Sciences-Council/Default.aspx>

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Registration, Deformable, PET/CT, Multimodal, Cancer Therapy

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

1. Junyu Chen (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)
2. M. Faizyab Ali Chaudhary (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)
3. Yihao Liu (Vanderbilt University, TN, USA)
4. Shuwen Wei (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)
5. Harrison Bai (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)
6. Yong Du (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)
7. Jing Tang (University of Cincinnati, OH, USA)
8. Adam Alessio (Michigan State University, MI, USA)
9. Alessa Hering (Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, Netherlands)
10. Aaron Carass (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Junyu Chen (jchen245@jhmi.edu)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, clinicians are part of the organizing team. The team includes a radiologist (H. Bai) and a board-certified medical physicist (Y. Du), who provide clinical expertise by defining clinically and dosimetrically meaningful problem settings, advising on evaluation metrics relevant to therapy planning and dose estimation, and interpreting results in the context of patient care. Their involvement ensures that the PSMAReg task remains closely aligned with real-world therapy planning and dosimetry workflows.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some

modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

This task is not associated with a standalone physical event. However, it is organized in close collaboration with the SNMMI Physics, Instrumentation, and Data Sciences Council (PIDSC), which supports dissemination, community engagement, and clinical relevance within the nuclear medicine and medical imaging communities.

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://learn2reg.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Private data is allowed but must be reported

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Organizers and team members of organizers may participate and are ranked but cannot win prizes.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

To be announced.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Challenge organizers may submit algorithms as baselines but cannot win prizes. Up to three (different) teams can win awards.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Participants must submit a short description of their methods via arXiv, based on their leaderboard results, to be eligible for test phase participation. Selected participants who contribute to the test phase will later (after the challenge concludes) be invited to submit a more detailed method description. These submissions will be compiled into the Learn2Reg proceedings, which may be published as an arXiv collection or included in open-access journals such as MELBA.

Participants in the test phase will also be invited to co-author the joint manuscript summarizing the challenge. Each team may contribute up to two authors, ideally the primary contributor and their senior author.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The validation and test submission processes are different:

- Validation leaderboard: The participating teams must submit their predictions (displacement fields) as a single compressed zip file via the grand-challenge.org interface. The tree directory structure will be described once the challenge is online.

- Test leaderboard: the participating teams are required to submit a short paper describing their method and a Docker container containing pre-trained models and training code. We encourage participants to only submit containers that can be run in a rootless mode to increase the usability of the submitted Docker containers on computational servers.

This design balances ease of participation during validation with stronger controls during final testing to ensure fair and reproducible evaluation on the private test set.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will get the opportunity to upload their algorithm output to be evaluated on the validation data of the validation phase in order to avoid any pitfalls (wrong orientation, etc.). We also provide our evaluation scripts to test them on the training data.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- Registration period: March 2026
 - Release date of the training set: March 2026
 - Release date of the validation set: March 2026
 - Start of the validation phase: April 2026
 - Start of the evaluation phase: August 2026
 - End of the evaluation phase: late-August 2026 (short description of the proposed technique, results on the validation set)
 - MICCAI 2026: presentation of results

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The training and validation data used in this challenge are derived from the publicly available autoPET III dataset [1], which was released in compliance with applicable ethics approvals and data use regulations. The Johns Hopkins University (JHU) dataset will not be shared publicly; all evaluation using this dataset will be performed locally at JHU through organizer-side execution of submitted methods. The collection and analysis of this internal dataset were conducted in compliance with all relevant ethical regulations and were approved by the Institutional Review Board at Johns Hopkins Hospital. This retrospective study received IRB approval with a waiver of written informed consent (IRB: CIR00349673).

1. Ingrisch, Matthias, et al. Automated Lesion Segmentation in Whole-Body PET/CT: Multitracer Multicenter Generalization. 27th International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention (MICCAI 2024), 2024. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990932>

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation code to evaluate performance is available at:

<https://github.com/JHU-MedImage-Reg/>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participating teams are encouraged but not required to make their code publicly available. We will provide links to available source code on the challenge website.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Data providers responsible for annotating the test cases will have access to the corresponding test labels. Organizers involved in implementing the evaluation metrics and scripts will also have limited access to test labels for the purpose of troubleshooting and internal code validation. To protect the privacy and integrity of the test data, full access to the complete set of test labels will be strictly restricted to a minimal number of authorized personnel.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis

- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Treatment planning, Research, Prognosis, Longitudinal study

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Registration

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for this task consists of real-world patients with prostate cancer who undergo whole-body PSMA PET/CT imaging at multiple sequential time points as part of clinical care. This includes patients imaged for therapy planning, patient-specific dosimetry, and therapy response assessment, with scans acquired before therapy and at one or more follow-up time points during or after treatment (e.g., external beam radiation therapy and radiopharmaceutical therapy).

In the intended clinical application, registration methods developed and evaluated in this task would be deployed to align these sequential PSMA PET/CT scans from the same patient, under conditions that reflect routine practice, including heterogeneous metastatic disease burden, variable patient positioning and bed placement, and therapy-related anatomical or pathological changes. This target cohort therefore represents the patient population for whom accurate whole-body PSMA PET/CT registration can directly support quantitative dose estimation, organ tolerance assessment, and treatment optimization.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of patients diagnosed with prostate cancer who underwent whole-body PSMA PET/CT imaging as part of routine clinical care. Training and validation data are derived from the autoPET PSMA dataset [1], which includes 597 whole-body PSMA PET/CT scans from 378 patients, with 164 patients having two or more sequential scans suitable for registration. All patients are male, with a mean age of 71.2 years (standard deviation 8.2 years; range 48–91 years), reflecting the typical demographic distribution of prostate cancer patients undergoing PSMA PET/CT imaging.

Test phase evaluation is performed on an independent internal cohort from Johns Hopkins University, comprising 262 whole-body PSMA PET/CT scans from 131 prostate cancer patients acquired using comparable clinical protocols. All patients are male, with a mean age of 72.6 years (standard deviation 8.7 years; range 53–93 years), reflecting the typical demographic distribution of prostate cancer patients undergoing PSMA PET/CT imaging. The cohort exhibits substantial variability in body habitus, disease burden, and patient positioning, introducing clinically meaningful challenges for sequential whole-body PSMA PET/CT registration.

1. Ingrisch, Matthias, et al. Automated Lesion Segmentation in Whole-Body PET/CT: Multitracer Multicenter Generalization. 27th International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention (MICCAI 2024), 2024. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990932>

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Positron emission tomography (PET); Low-dose Computed Tomography (CT)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

In addition to the image data, the challenge provides detailed contextual annotations that are directly associated with the imaging volumes and are designed to support clinically meaningful development and evaluation of registration methods.

For the training and validation datasets, lesion label maps on PSMA PET are provided from the autoPET challenge [1], delineating PSMA-avid lesions across the whole body. In parallel, automatic whole-body organ segmentations generated using TotalSegmentator are provided on the corresponding low-dose CT images. TotalSegmentator produces 117 anatomical labels, covering major organs, sub-organs, and relevant anatomical structures throughout the body, and these labels provide rich anatomical context for organ-aware registration and evaluation.

For the internal evaluation dataset used in the test phase, additional expert annotations are available but are not released to participants. These include TotalSegmentator-derived organ labels on CT and manual annotations on PSMA PET for both PSMA-avid organs and lesions. PSMA-avid organs include the salivary glands, lacrimal glands, kidneys, liver, spleen, small bowel, and urinary bladder, which are commonly considered dose-limiting organs in prostate cancer therapy. Manual lesion annotations are also provided to enable tumor-focused evaluation.

Evaluation is primarily conducted through organ-level label overlap mapping, reflecting the clinical priority in dosimetry to accurately estimate dose accumulation within dose-limiting normal organs, rather than within individual lesions. Accurate registration in these organs from sequential scans is critical for determining the maximum tolerable dose and for guiding therapy optimization. In addition, lesion-based evaluation is performed to assess tumor burden alignment and quantitative stability of PET-derived measures, including standardized uptake value (SUV) statistics, ensuring that lesion-level quantitative information is not adversely altered by the registration process.

Together, these contextual annotations and evaluation strategies are designed to align methodological development with real-world clinical priorities in PSMA-based therapy planning and dosimetry.

1. Ingrisich, Matthias, et al. Automated Lesion Segmentation in Whole-Body PET/CT: Multitracer Multicenter Generalization. 27th International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention (MICCAI 2024), 2024. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990932>

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Limited contextual information will be provided alongside the images, including patient age and imaging system metadata. No additional demographic details or medical history will be shared. All data are de-identified, and the challenge is designed to focus primarily on image-based registration while allowing participants to account for relevant acquisition-related variability.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The target entities for this challenge are whole-body anatomical and molecular regions imaged by PSMA PET/CT in patients with prostate cancer. In the final biomedical application, image data are acquired from the whole-body protocol, extending from the skull base to mid-thigh, and include both molecular PSMA PET uptake and anatomical information from low-dose CT.

The primary regions of interest include dose-limiting normal organs and tumor-bearing structures that are critical for therapy planning, dosimetry, and response assessment. These encompass PSMA-avid organs such as the salivary glands, lacrimal glands, kidneys, liver, spleen, small bowel, and urinary bladder, as well as metastatic lesions distributed throughout the skeletal system, lymph nodes, and soft tissues.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The participating algorithms are designed to perform whole-body registration of sequential PSMA PET/CT scans acquired from the same patient. The primary target is accurate spatial alignment of molecular PSMA PET uptake and anatomical CT structures across pre-therapy and follow-up scans, despite differences in patient positioning and therapy-related anatomical changes.

The algorithms are intended to support therapy planning and dosimetry workflows used by nuclear medicine physicians and medical physicists, with a focus on accurately aligning dose-limiting normal organs and tumor-bearing regions. These include PSMA-avid organs such as the salivary glands, lacrimal glands, kidneys, liver, spleen, small bowel, and urinary bladder, as well as metastatic lesions distributed throughout the body. The target is consistent across the challenge and target cohorts, with methods expected to generalize beyond the annotated challenge data to real-world clinical practice.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,Reliability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Both the autoPET dataset and the internal PSMA PET/CT evaluation dataset were acquired using the clinical PET/CT scanners. The imaging systems include Siemens Biograph mCT, Siemens Biograph 64, GE Discovery 690, GE Discovery RX, GE Discovery IQ, and Siemens Biograph Horizon scanners.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

For the autoPET PSMA dataset, examinations were acquired on multiple clinical PET/CT systems, including Siemens Biograph 64, Siemens Biograph 20 mCT, and GE Discovery 690 scanners. Imaging protocols typically included a diagnostic CT scan covering the skull base to mid-thigh, with a mean reference tube current-time product of approximately 140 mAs, tube voltages of 100 kV or 120 kV, and slice thicknesses ranging from 2.5 to 5 mm. Intravenous contrast enhancement was used in most cases, except where contraindicated. Whole-body PSMA PET scans were acquired on average 71 minutes after tracer injection, using either ^{18}F -labeled PSMA (mean injected activity 246 MBq; 369 studies) or ^{68}Ga -labeled PSMA (mean injected activity 214 MBq; 228 studies). PET images were reconstructed with attenuation correction derived from the corresponding CT data using standard vendor-provided reconstruction algorithms, such as ordered-subset expectation maximization (OSEM), with reconstructed slice thicknesses ranging from 3 to 5 mm (mean 3.5 mm).

For the JHU PSMA PET/CT evaluation dataset, images were acquired on GE Discovery RX, GE Discovery IQ, Siemens Biograph Horizon, and Siemens Biograph mCT TOF scanners using standardized whole-body imaging protocols covering the skull base to mid-thigh. Patients were injected with ^{18}F -DCFPyL at a dose of 3.67 MBq/kg and rested in a quiet environment for approximately 60 minutes prior to imaging. CT acquisition was performed first using 120 kV, a rotation time of 0.33 seconds, and automated exposure control (CareDOSE 4D), with a slice thickness of 3.0 mm and reconstruction to a 512×512 matrix, resulting in a voxel size of approximately $0.98 \times 0.98 \times 3.0 \text{ mm}^3$. PET acquisition followed with a bed speed of 2 mm/s. PET images were reconstructed using an OSEM3D plus time-of-flight algorithm with 2 iterations, 21 subsets, and 5 mm full width at half maximum Gaussian filtering. The PET reconstruction matrix size was 200×200 , yielding anisotropic voxel dimensions of approximately $4.07 \times 4.07 \times 3.0 \text{ mm}^3$.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The training and validation data are derived from the PSMA autoPET dataset, which was acquired at two large university hospitals in Germany, namely University Hospital Tübingen (UKT) and Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich (LMU), and released as part of the previous autoPET challenge.

The private evaluation dataset was acquired at Johns Hopkins University (JHU) in the United States as part of routine clinical PSMA PET/CT imaging. All data were collected and processed in compliance with local institutional policies and ethical regulations. No additional acquisition centers are disclosed beyond these institutions, as the provided information is sufficient to characterize the data sources while maintaining patient anonymity.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

For the autoPET PSMA dataset, data acquisition and annotation were performed by specialized clinical teams consisting of radiologists, nuclear medicine physicians, and experienced technologists. Manual segmentation of PSMA-avid tumor lesions was carried out by two radiologists with expertise in hybrid PET/CT imaging, ensuring high-quality and clinically consistent annotations.

For the JHU dataset, all cases were reviewed independently by two experienced radiologists prior to any lesion labeling or model development, one with 6 years of radiology experience and one with 5 years of experience in hybrid imaging. Any discrepancies were resolved by a third senior radiologist with 10 years of experience, providing expert consensus and quality assurance. Case inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied uniformly

and independently of clinical outcomes to minimize selection bias. Additional chart review, including pathology reports and follow-up multimodal imaging, was conducted to classify lesions and assess treatment response when applicable.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In this task, one case refers to a pair of sequential whole-body PSMA PET/CT scans from the same patient, acquired at two different time points (e.g., pre-therapy and follow-up). Each case encompasses all data required to compute a single registration result that is compared against the corresponding reference annotations.

For training and validation, each case consists of:

- One 3D whole-body PSMA PET volume and its corresponding low-dose CT volume from the first time point.
- One 3D whole-body PSMA PET volume and its corresponding low-dose CT volume from the follow-up time point.
- Associated context information for training and validation cases, including manual PSMA-avid lesion label maps on PET and automatic whole-body organ segmentations on CT generated using TotalSegmentator.

For testing, the evaluation is performed on an internal PSMA PET/CT dataset acquired at Johns Hopkins University, which is not released to participants. Participants are instead required to submit containerized implementations of their registration methods, which are executed locally by the organizers on the held-out evaluation cases. For these test cases, reference annotations, including manual lesion labels and organ annotations, are used exclusively for scoring and are not accessible to participants.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

- Training and validation cases are derived from the autoPET PSMA dataset and consist of 164 sequential cases constructed from patients with two or more scans. These cases are split using an 8:2 training-to-validation ratio: 1) Training set: 131 cases; 2) Validation set: 33 cases.

- In addition, PSMA PET/CT scans from 214 patients without sequential imaging in the autoPET dataset are also provided for training purposes only. These single-timepoint cases enable participants to explore inter-subject or population-based registration strategies and pretraining schemes that may improve downstream performance on sequential registration.

- Test cases are drawn from the internal Johns Hopkins University dataset and consist of 131 sequential cases,

corresponding to 262 PSMA PET/CT scans from 131 patients. The test data are not released to participants and are used exclusively for final evaluation through organizer-side execution of submitted methods.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

For the training and validation sets, CT images are annotated for normal organs, while PSMA-avid lesions are annotated on the corresponding PET images.

For the test set, both CT and PET images are annotated for normal organs and PSMA-avid organs, and PSMA-avid lesions are additionally annotated on PET.

All data in the training, validation, and test splits are fully annotated according to these definitions.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases and the 8:2 training-to-validation split were chosen to balance effective model development with reliable validation, while preserving a sufficiently large and fully independent test set for unbiased evaluation. Test cases are drawn from a separate clinical cohort acquired at Johns Hopkins University and are not released to participants, enabling robust assessment of generalization to unseen data and real-world clinical conditions. As this is the first public computational challenge focused specifically on whole-body PSMA PET/CT registration in a therapeutic setting, the dataset size was selected to be large enough to establish a meaningful benchmark while remaining feasible for participant training and deployment.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training, validation, and test cases reflect natural clinical distributions rather than artificially balanced subsets. The training and validation cases are derived from the autoPET PSMA dataset, while the test cases are drawn from an independent clinical cohort acquired at Johns Hopkins University. Although the datasets differ in acquisition site, scanner hardware, and reconstruction settings, the imaging protocols are similar, with all scans acquired using the whole-body PSMA PET/CT protocols covering the skull base to mid-thigh. This design introduces a controlled and clinically realistic distributional shift between development and evaluation data, which is a desired characteristic of the challenge. It enables assessment of the robustness and generalizability of registration methods under realistic deployment conditions. In addition, training data include both sequential scan pairs and single-timepoint cases to support inter-subject pretraining strategies, whereas validation and testing are performed exclusively on sequential cases to ensure fair and clinically relevant evaluation.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

This challenge makes deliberate use of unseen and unpublished data for evaluation. All test cases are drawn from an internal PSMA PET/CT dataset acquired at Johns Hopkins University, which has not been publicly released and is not accessible to participants. This evaluation dataset consists of 131 sequential cases, corresponding to 262 PSMA PET/CT scans from 131 patients.

In contrast, the training and validation data are derived from the publicly available autoPET PSMA dataset and include 164 sequential cases. As a result, 100% of the test data and approximately 44% of all cases used in the challenge (131 out of 295 total sequential cases) consist of previously unseen and unpublished data.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For the training and validation cases derived from the autoPET PSMA dataset, reference annotations consist of:

- Manual lesion label maps on PSMA PET, delineating PSMA-avid tumor lesions.
- Automatic whole-body organ segmentations on CT, generated using TotalSegmentator, which provides up to 117 anatomical organ and structure labels.

The lesion annotations serve as reference information for tumor-aware evaluation and method development, while the organ segmentations provide anatomical context for organ-level evaluation. These annotations are released to participants for training and validation.

For the test cases, reference annotations are generated internally and are not released to participants. They include:

- Manual annotations on PSMA PET for both PSMA-avid lesions and PSMA-avid normal organs, including the salivary glands, lacrimal glands, kidneys, liver, spleen, small bowel, and urinary bladder.
- Automatic organ segmentations on CT generated using TotalSegmentator.

These annotations are used exclusively by the organizers to compute evaluation metrics, primarily through organ-level label overlap mapping and lesion-based quantitative consistency checks.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For the autoPET PSMA training and validation cases, annotators followed a standardized annotation protocol defined for the autoPET challenge. The protocol consisted of two main steps:

- Identification of PSMA-avid tumor lesions through joint visual assessment of PET and CT images, informed by available clinical examination reports.
- Manual free-hand segmentation of the identified lesions on axial image slices.

For the JHU evaluation dataset, annotations were performed according to institutionally approved clinical protocols for PSMA PET/CT interpretation. PSMA-avid lesions and organs were first delineated using multiple manual thresholding levels on PET images on a slice-by-slice basis on axial image slices, followed by manual correction and refinement guided by anatomical information from CT. All annotations were performed using clinical-grade software after independent case review by experienced radiologists, with discrepancies resolved through consensus. Annotation protocols for the evaluation dataset were applied consistently across cases and were not disclosed to participants to preserve the integrity of the held-out test set.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For the autoPET dataset, manual lesion annotations were performed by two board-certified radiologists with expertise in hybrid PET/CT imaging, supported by specialized nuclear medicine teams and experienced technologists involved in data acquisition.

For the JHU dataset, all cases were independently annotated by two experienced radiologists (5 and 6 years of professional experience, respectively). Discrepancies were identified through case-by-case comparison of lesion masks and organ delineations. Disagreements were resolved during a structured consensus review meeting. If consensus could not be reached immediately, a third senior radiologist (10 years of experience) adjudicated the case and made the final determination. The final reference annotation reflects the adjudicated consensus mask.

Automatic organ segmentations on CT were generated using TotalSegmentator. To mitigate potential inaccuracies, all segmentations underwent visual quality control by the task organizers, each of whom has more than 5 years of experience in medical imaging research. Gross anatomical errors (e.g., missing organs, obvious mislabeling, or severe boundary leakage) were corrected or excluded prior to release. Minor boundary imperfections were retained to reflect realistic clinical variability. Organ labels are used for organ-level overlap evaluation and anatomical context rather than as pixel-perfect anatomical ground truth.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For cases with multiple human annotators (JHU evaluation dataset), each case was first annotated independently by two radiologists. The two masks were compared, and discrepancies were reviewed in a structured consensus meeting. A third senior radiologist adjudicated unresolved disagreements. The final released reference annotation corresponds to the adjudicated consensus mask.

For the autoPET dataset, lesion annotations follow the original challenge curation protocol, which included dual-reader review and consensus refinement prior to public release.

Automatic CT organ segmentations generated using TotalSegmentator were subjected to visual quality control. Where corrections were required, they were manually refined before inclusion in the reference set.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For the training and validation cases, the original clinical PSMA PET/CT images are provided with minimal pre-processing. The raw imaging data is converted from DICOM to NIfTI format to facilitate standardized data handling and interoperability across methods. No additional pre-processing steps, such as intensity normalization, resampling, cropping, denoising, or registration, are applied by the organizers. Participants are free to apply any additional pre-processing steps within their own pipelines.

For the test cases, the original PSMA PET/CT images are similarly converted from DICOM to NIfTI format and are

otherwise left unprocessed. The test data are not distributed to participants; instead, submitted methods are executed by the organizers on the held-out test images under the same minimal pre-processing conditions.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The main sources of annotation error arise from manual delineation of PSMA-avid lesions and organs on PET, where boundaries are often ill-defined due to limited spatial resolution, image noise, partial volume effects, and heterogeneous tracer uptake. Variability is more pronounced for small lesions and for lesions adjacent to physiologically PSMA-avid organs. Additional uncertainty may arise from residual PET-CT misregistration within a single imaging session, caused by patient motion or respiratory effects.

For the training and validation cases (autoPET PSMA), errors may stem from subjective lesion identification and manual free-hand segmentation. While explicit inter- and intra-annotator variability measures are not available, prior PET segmentation studies suggest segmentation volume uncertainty is on the order of 5-30% [1].

For the test cases (JHU dataset), annotation uncertainty is introduced by manual multi-thresholding followed by slice-by-slice correction and differences in expert interpretation. This variability is mitigated through independent review by two radiologists and consensus adjudication by a senior radiologist. Automatic organ segmentations from TotalSegmentator may introduce minor boundary inaccuracies, particularly in anatomically distorted regions, but these effects are consistent across cases and have limited impact on overlap-based evaluation. Severely misaligned PET-CT cases were excluded during dataset curation to ensure reliable anatomical correspondence for evaluation.

1. Ingrisich, Matthias, et al. Automated Lesion Segmentation in Whole-Body PET/CT: Multitracer Multicenter Generalization. 27th International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention (MICCAI 2024), 2024. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990932>

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Additional sources of error include image artifacts in PET and/or CT, such as motion artifacts, metal-induced streaking in CT, or noise and attenuation-related artifacts in PET, which may alter local image appearance and intensity distributions.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

1. Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC): For each case, we first obtain a deformation field: in the validation phase, this is the field submitted by the participant; in the test phase, it is the field generated when their Docker container is executed. We use this deformation field to warp the moving-image organ label map into the fixed-image space. We then compute DSC between the warped moving and fixed organ label maps to measure volumetric overlap. DSC is computed for each organ; the per-subject DSC is the average DSC across all organs in that case. For validation and test rankings, we aggregate across subjects by reporting the mean and standard deviation of per-subject DSC. DSC is reported separately for CT-derived organ labels and PET-derived organ labels.

2. 95th percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95): For each case, we use the same deformation field (submitted in validation or produced by the Docker container in the test phase) to warp the moving-image organ label map into the fixed-image space. We then compute the 95th percentile Hausdorff distance (HD95) between the warped moving and fixed organ label maps to quantify boundary alignment. HD95 is computed for each organ; the per-subject HD95 is the average HD95 across all organs in that case. For validation and test rankings, we aggregate across subjects by reporting the mean and standard deviation of per-subject HD95. HD95 is reported separately for CT-derived organ labels and PET-derived organ labels, with lower values indicating better boundary correspondence.

3. Non-diffeomorphic volume percentage (NDV) [1]: For each case, we compute NDV directly from the deformation field by evaluating the Jacobian determinant at each voxel. NDV is defined as the percentage of voxels with a non-positive Jacobian determinant, which indicates local foldings and, therefore, non-diffeomorphic behavior. NDV is computed once per subject (one deformation field per case). For validation and test rankings, we aggregate across subjects by reporting the mean and standard deviation of NDV. Lower NDV (ideally close to 0) indicates a more regular and physically plausible deformation.

4. Metabolic Tumor Volume (MTV) bias: For each case, we compute MTV from the moving-image PET lesion label map as the total physical volume (mL) of voxels within the lesion mask. We then warp the moving-image lesion labels into the fixed-image space using the participant's deformation field, recompute MTV from the warped lesion labels, and report the percentage bias relative to the original moving-image MTV. MTV bias is computed once per subject. For validation and test rankings, we aggregate across subjects by reporting the mean and standard deviation of MTV bias. Bias closer to 0 indicates better preservation of lesion volume under deformation.

5. Total Lesion Glycolysis (TLG) bias: For each case, we compute TLG on the moving image from the PET lesion labels by taking the lesion volume (MTV) and scaling it by the mean SUV within the lesion mask. We then warp the moving PET image into the fixed-image space using the participant's deformation field and recompute TLG in the same way, using the corresponding warped lesion mask. We report the percentage bias between the TLG computed from the original moving PET and the TLG computed after warping. TLG bias is computed once per subject. For validation and test rankings, we aggregate across subjects by reporting the mean and standard deviation of TLG bias. Bias closer to 0 indicates better preservation of PET-derived quantitative tumor burden.

Each of the above metrics maps directly to the challenge aims. DSC and HD95 evaluate registration accuracy by measuring volumetric overlap and boundary correspondence, respectively, using organ labels in fixed-image space. MTV and TLG bias evaluate quantitative fidelity by assessing whether the deformation preserves PET-derived lesion burden measures after warping (i.e., avoiding volume and uptake drift). NDV evaluates plausibility/regularity by quantifying non-diffeomorphic behavior (foldings) in the deformation field.

1. Liu, Yihao, et al. "On finite difference jacobian computation in deformable image registration." (2024). International Journal of Computer Vision.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

DSC and HD95 quantify anatomical alignment accuracy and boundary consistency in dose-limiting organs on both PET and CT, which are central to reliable dose accumulation and therapy planning.

HD95 complements DSC by emphasizing robustness to localized misregistration. The non-diffeomorphic volume percentage evaluates deformation regularity and physical plausibility, ensuring that estimated transformations do not introduce unrealistic anatomical distortions.

The inclusion of MTV and TLG bias metrics reflects a key requirement of therapeutic PSMA PET/CT registration: the registration process should not artificially alter PET-derived quantitative information. MTV and TLG are clinically relevant molecular imaging biomarkers used for tumor burden estimation, response assessment, and therapy optimization. By evaluating bias in these measures after warping, we assess whether registration preserves lesion volume and uptake-derived statistics without introducing quantitative drift, which is important for downstream dosimetry and longitudinal analyses. Without these metrics, participants may optimize for visual or anatomical alignment alone while inadvertently distorting PET quantification.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The challenge will use a multi-metric ranking scheme inspired by the Medical Segmentation Decathlon and Learn2Reg challenges. For each metric listed above, we will rank the participating methods. However, rather than simply averaging raw metric values (which have different scales and importances), we will convert each metric result into a normalized rank score. The procedure is as follows: for a given metric (say, mean fissure PRAUC), we perform pairwise statistical comparisons between all methods to determine if differences are significant. If one method significantly outperforms another on that metric ($p < 0.05$), it is considered to "win" that comparison. We then produce a ranking of methods for that metric based on the number of wins. This yields an ordering where some methods might be statistically tied. We then map these ranks to a score between 0.1 and 1.0 for that metric (with the top method(s) getting 1.0, and the bottom method getting 0.1, for example). This approach of "significant ranking" ensures we don't over-penalize methods that are practically equivalent to each other. We will do this for each primary metric and once each method has a score for each metric, we compute an aggregate score as the geometric mean of its metric scores.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

In the final evaluation, since we will run each algorithm's Docker on all test cases, we expect a complete set of results for each method. If a Docker submission fails to produce output for one or more test cases (e.g., due to a crash or timeout), we will handle it as follows: If the failure is minor (e.g., one case missing due to a known bug), we will assign that method the worst possible metric values for that case (essentially penalizing heavily). If a method fails on a substantial number of cases or fails to run entirely, it will be disqualified from ranking. We will

communicate with teams if a container fails to try to resolve any technical issues (within reason and time constraints).

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking scheme is chosen to balance multiple objectives fairly and robustly. The geometric mean of metric scores is particularly suitable because it rewards consistency: a method that is uniformly good across all metrics will outrank a method that is excellent in one metric but poor in another.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The main statistical tool we will use is the Wilcoxon signed-rank test (non-parametric paired test) to compare methods for each metric. This test does not assume normal distribution and is appropriate for comparing two algorithms across multiple cases. For each pair of methods A and B, we will test the null hypothesis that there is no difference in their performance distribution (e.g., Dice differences have zero median). A two-sided p value less than 0.05 will be considered to be significantly different.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

To quantify the precision of each evaluation metric, we will compute 95% confidence intervals using nonparametric bootstrapping. Specifically, we will approximate the sampling distribution of each metric by repeatedly resampling the observed cases with replacement and recomputing the metric. The 95% confidence interval will then be derived from the empirical distribution of the bootstrap estimates, for example using percentile or bias-corrected and accelerated (BCa) intervals.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across test cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

We will assess performance variability across test cases using summary statistics such as the mean, standard deviation, and interquartile range (IQR). Variability will be visualized using boxplots and distribution plots to highlight dispersion and potential outliers.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

We will assess ranking variability by analyzing how algorithm ranks change across resampled test cases. This will allow us to perform pairwise comparisons across all methods using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test and rank methods based on the number of statistically significant wins, allowing score sharing in the presence of ties. To ensure robust comparisons we will use bootstrapping for repeated sampling.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is standard paired comparisons since it accounts for the paired nature of results (each algorithm produces one result per case, so methods can be compared case-by-case). It's more appropriate than an unpaired test since the same cases are used by all methods, reducing variance. We choose a

non-parametric test because metric distributions (especially Dice or TRE differences) might not be normal, and because performance data often have outliers or are bounded.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Missing data are not expected during the final test phase. All participating methods are submitted as Docker containers and executed by the organizers on every test case, ensuring complete and consistent result generation across all submissions.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

We will use software like pandas and numpy for data handling, SciPy or statsmodels for tests, and potentially scikit-learn or custom scripts for any additional analyses.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will provide several baseline algorithms to compare new methods against, there are:

- VoxelMorph (IEEE TMI'19)
- TransMorph (MedIA'22)
- VFA (SPIE JMI'24)
- ANTs, NiftyReg, Deeds

Where necessary, lightweight or memory-efficient configurations will be provided to ensure feasibility on whole-body volumes with standard GPU resources.

TASK 2: Learn2Breath: Unsupervised Lung CT Registration Under Large Deformation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is responsible for progressive damage to the lung parenchyma, pulmonary airways, and the vasculature. These structural changes can impact tissue distensibility and cause biomechanical impairments often leading to lung function decline. Deformable image registration (DIR) of the end-inspiratory and end-expiratory chest CT volumes is used to quantify local biomechanical abnormalities within the lung. DIR has been used to derive several biomarkers of lung function decline and adverse clinical outcomes in COPD and related obstructive lung disorders. An accurate assessment of these biomarkers, however, relies on the accuracy of the DIR which is challenging due to large anatomical changes (e.g. the diaphragm motion and airway collapse). The Learn2Breath challenge aims to advance DIR methods by providing a challenging problem and a large dataset to benchmark algorithms on inspiratory-to-expiratory 3D lung CT images. In this challenge, participants must develop fully automatic methods to accurately align an expiratory (moving) scan to its corresponding inspiratory (fixed) scan for the same subject. The dataset will be drawn from the multicenter Genetic Epidemiology of COPD (COPDGene) cohort, focusing on cases with the largest lung volume change between inspiration and expiration (approximately 1,000 image pairs) [1]. Our experimental setting makes the task challenging in two unique ways: we focus on DIR of volumes with the largest possible change in volumes, and we assign the inspiratory volume space as the reference. Accurate DIR for large deformation would help understand early lung disease. We choose inspiratory volumes as the reference because it is most commonly protocolled in clinical settings and any DIR biomarker should be available in the same space for characterization and comparison.

Without manual landmarks for training or evaluation, Learn2Breath introduces novel surrogate evaluation metrics based on anatomical structures. In particular, we propose to use a state-of-the-art, pulmonary fissure segmentation method, FissureNet [2], to evaluate how well the major lung fissures (which separate the lobes) are aligned by the registration method. Overlap of fissure regions after registration will serve as a unique overlap metric measuring the quality of alignment within the lung. Additional evaluation criteria will include the overlap of lung boundaries and lobes, and the physical plausibility of the deformation (measured by the percentage of folding or non-invertible regions). Another important metric would be the alignment of the diaphragm (especially at the costophrenic angles). Diaphragm alignment will be assessed by focusing on the costophrenic recesses, the sharp angles where the diaphragm meets the chest wall laterally, as these are regions of significant motion. Our use of fissure and diaphragm alignment as quantitative measures is novel in terms of lung registration and clinically relevant as well.

Our challenge will facilitate the development of robust, unsupervised image registration models for pulmonary images. For model development, we will provide only the chest CT images (inspiratory-expiratory image pairs) for training while keeping evaluation masks and metrics private. The impact of the challenge will be both technical

and clinical: technically, it will establish new benchmarks for deformable registration on large-deformation 3D CT data; clinically, it will generate more reliable DIR methods to compute lung function measures (like regional ventilation) from routine CT scans, which could aid early diagnosis, treatment planning, and longitudinal assessment in COPD and other lung conditions.

[1] Regan, Elizabeth A., et al. "Genetic epidemiology of COPD (COPDGene) study design." *COPD: Journal of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease* 7.1 (2011): 32-43.

[2] Gerard, Sarah E., et al. "FissureNet: A deep learning approach for pulmonary fissure detection in CT images." *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 38.1 (2018): 156-166.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Image Registration, Large Deformation, Lung, Chest CT, COPD, Unsupervised Learning

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

1. Muhammad Faizyab Ali Chaudhary (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)
2. Junyu Chen (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)
3. Sarah E. Gerard (University of Iowa, IA, USA)
4. Joseph M. Reinhardt (University of Iowa, IA, USA)
5. Gary E. Christensen (University of Iowa, IA, USA)
6. Aaron Carass (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Muhammad Faizyab Ali Chaudhary (mchaud25@jh.edu)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Clinicians can possibly join the challenge organization in cases where significant clinical oversight is required. Such cases include an assessment of lung tissue textures that are hard to characterize before and after image registration.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

N/A

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://learn2reg.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Private data is allowed but must be reported

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Organizers and team members of organizers may participate and are ranked but cannot win prizes.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

To be announced.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Challenge organizers may submit algorithms as baselines but cannot win prizes. Up to three (different) teams can win awards.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Participants must submit a short description of their methods via arXiv, based on their leaderboard results, to be eligible for test phase participation. Selected participants who contribute to the test phase will later (after the challenge concludes) be invited to submit a more detailed method description. These submissions will be compiled into the Learn2Reg proceedings, which may be published as an arXiv collection or included in open-access journals such as MELBA.

Participants in the test phase will also be invited to co-author the joint manuscript summarizing the challenge. Each team may contribute up to two authors, ideally the primary contributor and their senior author.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The validation and test submission processes are different:

- Validation leaderboard: The participating teams must submit their predictions (displacement fields) as a single compressed zip file via the grand-challenge.org interface. The tree directory structure will be described once the challenge is online.

- Test leaderboard: the participating teams are required to submit a short paper describing their method and a Docker container containing pre-trained models and training code. We encourage participants to only submit containers that can be run in a rootless mode to increase the usability of the submitted Docker containers on computational servers.

This choice is a trade-off between reducing the participant's workload and limiting the risk of cheating for the final ranking.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will get the opportunity to upload their algorithm output to be evaluated on the validation data of the validation phase in order to avoid any pitfalls (wrong orientation, etc.). We also provide our evaluation scripts to test them on the training data.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- Registration period: March 2026
 - Release date of the training set: March 2026
 - Release date of the validation set: March 2026
 - Start of the validation phase: April 2026
 - Start of the evaluation phase: August 2026
 - End of the evaluation phase: late-August 2026 (short description of the proposed technique, results on the validation set)
 - MICCAI 2026: presentation of results

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The imaging data for this challenge will be derived from the COPDGene study (ClinicalTrials.gov identifier NCT00608764), which obtained informed consent and institutional review board approvals at each of its 21 participating clinical centers. For the purposes of this challenge, we are requesting permission through an ancillary study proposal to use and share a subset of COPDGene CT scans. Since the data are de-identified and were previously collected under ethical approval, additional IRB approval specific to the challenge is expected to be exempt or expedited at our institutions; however, we will formally confirm this prior to data release. All participants will be required to agree to terms of data use that prohibit any attempt to re-identify individuals. We also note that the COPDGene images are largely publicly available to researchers upon application, and our use will comply with all original study's ethical guidelines and data usage policies.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)

- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation code to evaluate performance is available at:

<https://github.com/JHU-MedImage-Reg/>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participating teams are encouraged but not required to make their code publicly available. We will provide links to available source code on the challenge website.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This challenge does not have direct corporate sponsors influencing the results. However, we acknowledge the support of the COPDGene study, from which the data are derived. COPDGene was supported by NHLBI (National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute) grants U01 HL089897 and U01 HL089856 and by NIH contract 75N92023D00011. The COPDGene study (NCT00608764) has also been supported by the COPD Foundation through contributions to an Industry Advisory Committee including AstraZeneca, Bayer, Boehringer-Ingelheim, Genentech, GlaxoSmithKline, Novartis, Pfizer, and Sunovion. These funding sources enabled the collection of the data but they have no role in the design or outcomes of this challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis

- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Prognosis, Research, Intervention planning, Treatment planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Registration

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target population for this technology is patients undergoing thoracic CT imaging who have diseases or conditions affecting lung function. This includes individuals with COPD, emphysema, asthma, or other causes of air trapping and respiratory mechanics changes. In clinical practice, such patients (often middle-aged to older adults, both male and female) often have inspiratory/expiratory CT scans taken to assess structural changes and assess biomechanical properties of the lung tissue. The algorithms developed could also be applied to lung cancer patients' 4D CT scans (to align phases for radiation planning) or generally any scenario requiring alignment of lungs in different inflation states. The inclusion criteria in a real-world application would typically be adult patients

who can perform breath-hold CT scans at full inspiration and full expiration; this spans a broad range of lung health, from healthy smokers to severe COPD patients (GOLD stage 1 - 4). By improving registration, the end goal is to enable more accurate measurements (like regional volume change, ventilation, or strain) that can improve diagnosis or monitoring of lung diseases.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge data come from the COPDGene study, a large multi-center study focused on COPD. The subset we will use consists of pairs of chest CT scans (inspiration and expiration) from approximately 1,000 subjects. COPDGene enrolled approximately 10,000 subjects across 21 centers in the US. All participants, including current and former smokers, aged between 45 and 80 years, had a range of COPD severity (from never smoking controls to very severe, across GOLD 0 - 4). For each subject, chest CT volumes at end-inhalation (defined as total lung capacity (TLC)) and at end-exhalation (defined as functional residual capacity (FRC)) were acquired in the same session. In healthy adults, TLC typically ranges from 4 – 6 L, with slightly higher values observed in individuals with COPD, ranging from 4.8 L (SD 1.3 L) to 5.9 L (SD 1.5 L) (1, 2), and up to 6.7 L (SD 0.2 L) in some studies (1, 2). Residual volume (RV) has been reported to range from 2.0 L (SD 0.5 L) to 3.2 L (SD 0.8 L) in COPD (1, 2). We will select the 1,000 subjects with the largest change in lung volume between inspiration and expiration (as measured from the CT scans). By focusing on these “most challenging” cases (i.e., those with the greatest lung deflation from inhale to exhale), we ensure the registration task is particularly difficult and meaningful. These subjects likely include those with healthier lungs (able to exhale a large fraction of air) as well as some with moderate COPD who still had significant volume change. The challenge cohort is diverse in terms of sex and includes both Non-Hispanic White and African American individuals. All chest CT scans are non-contrast, thin-slice volumetric images of the thorax, covering from the lung apices down through the costophrenic angles (entire lung volume). The imaging was performed on various scanner models (GE, Siemens, Philips, etc.) across sites, at approximately 0.7 mm slice thickness for inspiration and 0.7 – 2.5 mm for expiration (expiration scans in COPDGene were often acquired at lower dose and slightly thicker slices). Despite differences, all images will be preprocessed to a common format as described below. In summary, the challenge cohort represents a difficult intra-subject registration scenario with large deformations and heterogeneous lung pathology, providing a rigorous testbed for registration algorithms.

1. Smith BM, Kirby M, Hoffman EA, Kronmal RA, Aaron SD, Allen NB, et al. Association of Dysanapsis With Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Among Older Adults. *JAMA* 2020;323:2268.

2. Comellas AP, Newell JD, Kirby M, Sieren JP, Peterson S, Hatt C, et al. Residual Volume versus FRC Computed Tomography Assessment of Functional Small Airway Disease in Smokers with and without Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2023;207:1536–1539.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Three-dimensional Computed Tomography (CT) of the chest (thoracic CT scans). Each case consists of two CT volumes of the lungs from the same subject: one acquired at full inspiration (high lung volume) and one at full expiration (low lung volume). The CT scans are high-resolution (sub-millimeter voxel spacing), which is necessary to capture fine structures like airways and fissures.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Participants will be given preprocessed chest CT images for each case (in NIfTI format) and a list pairing each inspiration scan with its corresponding expiration scan. We do not plan to provide extensive annotations (like landmarks or segmentations) for training, to keep the task unsupervised. A small subset of annotations (~5 - 10 samples) will be provided for validation. A simple automated lung segmentation will be applied to all scans to generate binary lung masks (encompassing the left and right lungs together). These masks can help participants by delineating the region of interest and excluding irrelevant areas. We will provide the computed total lung volume at inspiration and expiration for each case (in milliliters), since those can be derived from the lung masks; this could be useful for normalization or analysis. No manual landmarks or ground-truth deformation fields will be provided. The images will all be pre-aligned to the same orientation (e.g., RAS orientation) and resampled to a uniform voxel size (see pre-processing below), so that participants can directly work with the voxel data without worrying about divergent scanner coordinates. Each image pair will share the same spatial frame of reference after preprocessing (i.e., if we apply an initial alignment, the two volumes will already be roughly aligned in space except for the breathing differences). We will not release fissure or lobe segmentations to participants, as those are reserved for evaluation; the challenge emphasizes algorithms that do not rely on ground-truth correspondences. Participants will thus train and tune their methods using only image similarity (intensity information) and perhaps any derived features they choose to compute (like their own segmentation or keypoints, if their method uses such features). In summary, a small subset of annotations (for ~5 to 10 samples) will be provided.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

We will not provide demographic or clinical data, as it is not directly needed for the registration task. Some general information about the cohort can be summarized (e.g., all subjects are smokers, mix of COPD and non-COPD, age range ~45 - 80, both genders). We do not plan to release per-subject clinical variables (such as exact age, sex, COPD status, etc.), to keep the focus on the image-based task. The only potentially relevant numeric context is the lung volume change for each case, but since we selected cases by that criterion, participants already know these are large-change cases. Nonetheless, we might include a relative metric such as the percentage volume change from inspiration to expiration for each case as part of the data description (for example, "Case 1: 5.1L to 3.0L (41% volume reduction)"), which could help participants understand the range of deformation magnitudes they need to handle. This would not be an input to algorithms per se, just informational. No patient-identifying information will be present.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The images depict the thorax (chest) with focus on the lungs. In the CT scans, we see the lung parenchyma, pulmonary airways and vessels, the pleural surfaces, the chest wall, and portions of surrounding structures (heart, spine, diaphragm, etc.). The primary region of interest for registration is the lung itself – specifically aligning the lung tissue and lobar structures. The inspiratory and expiratory scans are from the same person, so the overall anatomy (rib cage, spine, etc.) is similar, but internal lung structures shift and compress. The target region includes the entire lungs from apex to base (including the diaphragm boundary at the base, which moves

upward on expiration). We also implicitly consider structures like the pulmonary fissures (the thin membranes between lobes) as important features to align. For evaluation, we will look at alignment quality within the lungs (lobes, fissures) and at the lung surfaces (including the costophrenic recess at the diaphragm). The challenge cohort and target cohort are essentially the same anatomical region – human lungs imaged in vivo by CT.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The participating algorithms should aim to accurately align all corresponding lung structures between the two scans. Key structures of interest include: the lobes of the lungs (right lung: upper, middle, lower lobes; left lung: upper and lower lobes) – these are separated by the fissures; the pulmonary fissures themselves (which appear as thin curvilinear surfaces inside the lung); the lung boundaries (the outer surfaces of the lungs against the pleura/chest wall and against the diaphragm); and internal structures such as large airways and blood vessels (though we do not explicitly evaluate vessels, a good registration should also align major vascular tree branches). In particular, the algorithms must handle the large diaphragm motion – at full expiration the diaphragm domes are significantly higher in the chest than at full inspiration. Accurately mapping the diaphragm region from expiration to inspiration is a challenging target (and one of our evaluation criteria). To summarize, the registration should produce a dense correspondence field that, when applied to the moving (expiratory) image, brings all lung anatomical features (lobes, fissures, surfaces, etc.) into the best possible alignment with those in the fixed (inspiratory) image.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,Reliability,Runtime,Complexity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The CT scans in this challenge were acquired on a variety of modern multi-detector CT scanners as part of a multi-center study. COPDGene used standard chest CT imaging protocols on scanners from major vendors (General Electric, Siemens, Philips). The exact scanner models and settings varied by site and time, but all were high-resolution spiral CT systems capable of sub-millimeter slice thickness. Importantly, each subject's inspiratory and expiratory scan were done on the same scanner within a single session (back-to-back scans). No additional

devices were used for registration ground truth (i.e., there was no external tracking system as correspondences were not directly measured). For the evaluation metrics, we rely on CT-derived segmentations (obtained via software, see below) rather than any physical tracking.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

In COPDGene, the inspiratory CT (often referred to as full-inspiration or total lung capacity scan) was typically acquired at near full dose, with parameters like 120 kVp and ~200 mAs, yielding high-quality images. The slice thickness was around 0.7 mm with in-plane pixel spacing ~0.6-0.8 mm. The expiratory CT (at functional residual capacity or residual volume) was often done at reduced dose (e.g., lower mAs) to minimize radiation, and in some cases with slightly thicker slices (up to 2.5 mm) to further reduce dose. Both scans covered from the apex of the lung to below the costophrenic angles (ensuring the entire diaphragm is included). Patients were scanned in supine position, instructed to hold their breath at full inhale and full exhale respectively. The time between the two scans was just a couple of minutes (enough for the subject to exhale after the first scan). As a result, patient positioning is nearly identical between scans (they did not get off the table). However, minor shifts can occur (e.g., slight couch movement or patient adjusting), so there may be small translations or rotations between the two volumes – these will be corrected in preprocessing. The image reconstruction kernel was standard for lung (a medium-sharp kernel to visualize lung detail). No contrast agent was used. In summary, the data are standard lung CTs differing mainly in lung inflation level.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The scans come from the COPDGene Phase 1 dataset. COPDGene is a multi-center study with 21 participating clinical sites across the United States (including academic medical centers such as National Jewish Health, Brigham & Women's Hospital, etc.). Scans from all these sites are included, providing a mix of scanner manufacturers and patient populations. The raw data were obtained via the COPDGene Data Coordinating Center. While COPDGene is not an open-access dataset, it is accessible to researchers upon request; our challenge uses a subset under an agreement with the study. We will credit the data source appropriately.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The CT acquisition in COPDGene was performed by trained radiology technologists at each site, following a standardized protocol. The subjects were coached to achieve full inspiration and expiration. All subjects are adults (no pediatric cases). They are predominantly smokers/ex-smokers, many with COPD, with some scans with significant emphysema, airway wall thickening, or other abnormalities. The inclusion of multiple sites and operators inevitably introduces some variability (for instance, slightly different breath-hold levels if a subject didn't exhale fully, or minor patient motion). These variabilities mimic real-world conditions and make the challenge more relevant. There was no single operator; over 20 sites contributed, each with their radiology staff. All scans went through quality control in the COPDGene study, and those with major issues (e.g., large motion artifacts) would have been excluded or rescanned. We will avoid using any scans with severe artifacts. Overall, the data acquisition reflects typical clinical practice across many hospitals.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In this task, one case refers to a matched pair of 3D CT images (the inspiratory CT and the expiratory CT of the same subject). This pair constitutes the input for an algorithm to produce one registration result. The expected output for a case is typically a deformation field (or a warped image) that aligns the moving image (expiration) to the fixed image (inspiration). Thus, a case is essentially one patient's two scans. All evaluation metrics (Dice scores, etc.) will be computed per case by comparing the deformed moving image's structures to the fixed image's structures. Both training and test "cases" follow this format of paired images.

b) Number of cases: We plan to provide a large training set on the order of hundreds of cases, and use a held-out test set of around 50 to 100 cases. Specifically, we anticipate releasing roughly 800 image pairs for training, selected from the COPDGene dataset. The validation set (for leaderboard feedback) will likely include about 20 cases. The test set for final evaluation will consist of approximately 50 to 100 cases (predominantly those with the largest volume changes). These numbers will be adjusted slightly based on final data availability and balancing considerations, but the goal is to have a sufficiently large training set for data-hungry methods and a very robust test set for evaluation.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

We plan to provide a large training set on the order of hundreds of cases, and use a held-out test set of around 50 to 100 cases. Specifically, we anticipate releasing roughly 800 image pairs for training, selected from the COPDGene dataset. The validation set (for leaderboard feedback) will likely include about 20 cases. The test set for final evaluation will consist of approximately 50 to 100 cases (predominantly those with the largest volume changes). These numbers may be adjusted slightly based on final data availability and balancing considerations, but the goal is to have a sufficiently large training set for data-hungry methods and a very robust test set for evaluation.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data across all splits are fully annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

A substantial number of training cases is provided to facilitate the development of learning-based registration algorithms. Deep learning models, in particular, require many examples to generalize well, and our challenge emphasizes unsupervised learning where the network can leverage lots of unlabeled data. We have chosen ~800 training pairs as a balance between diversity and manageability (it provides many examples of different anatomies and deformation magnitudes without being unwieldy in data size). The validation set is a smaller subset of challenging cases, enabling participants to gauge performance and debug issues ahead of the final test. By keeping the test set separate (and unreleased), we ensure the final ranking is unbiased by any method tuning

directly on those cases. A reasonably sized test set (50 - 100) means we can compute statistically meaningful comparisons and also evaluate consistency across subgroups (e.g., performance in upper vs. lower lobes, etc.).

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

All the provided pairs are intra-patient (same patient, two phases). There is no class label like in classification tasks, but one could consider that each pair has an associated “difficulty” roughly related to the volume change magnitude.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The majority of the challenge data has not been publicly used before. While COPDGene images have been used in research papers, the specific set of segmentations (fissures, lobes) that we will use for evaluation have never been published or made public. In particular, we will generate fissure masks for all cases specifically for this challenge, and these constitute new “labels” not available elsewhere. Therefore, the test annotations are completely unseen by participants and the community. The training data images themselves, being from a well-studied cohort, might have been seen in some context by some researchers, but since no ground-truth correspondences exist, prior exposure does not confer an advantage.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Since manual landmark annotation for thousands of scans is infeasible, we rely on automatic methods to create reference annotations for evaluation. Specifically, for each CT image we will generate: (1) a lung mask (delineating the entire lungs), (2) lobe masks (delineating each of the five lobes), (3) fissure segmentation (a mask of the fissure surfaces), and (4) diaphragm landmark(s) (points or curves at the costophrenic angles). The lung masks will be obtained via a standard automatic lung segmentation algorithm (such as thresholding + morphological cleanup or a pre-trained U-Net for lung fields). The fissure and lobe segmentations will be obtained using FissureNet, which has demonstrated state-of-the-art performance in identifying pulmonary fissures. The FissureNet segmentations will undergo manual review to ensure their quality before inclusion in evaluation. All FissureNet segmentations will be analyzed and manually corrected by 3 to 4 trained experts who will be supervised by a board-certified radiologist. If there is no consensus amongst the reviewer, the case will be inspected by the radiologist for final decision.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Because our “annotations” are algorithmically generated, there is no need for a human instruction protocol as in a typical manual segmentation task. Instead, we follow protocols described in the literature for the methods used. For example, FissureNet’s procedure for fissure detection is detailed in and we adhere to that approach for consistency. Essentially, FissureNet was trained on manually annotated fissures from an independent dataset and

is applied here as-is. For the diaphragm landmarks, if we did involve any manual step, it would simply be identifying the lowest point of the lung in a few scans to validate our automatic extraction. We anticipate fully automating that via code. Thus, there is no separate annotation training phase or inter-annotator instructions to describe. The only "protocol" is that any manual verification will be done by experienced imaging scientists (from our organizing team) to ensure the automatic labels make anatomical sense (e.g., checking that what the algorithm marked as fissure indeed corresponds to the known fissure location). If any manual refinement is needed (for example, to mark a fissure gap as incomplete), it will be done conservatively and uniformly across cases following standard anatomical definitions (major fissures separating upper/lower lobes, etc.). All such steps will be documented in the challenge report.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Ground truth fissure segmentations that were used for training FissureNet were generated in two steps. Fissure probabilities were obtained using a commercial software package (Apollo, VIDA Diagnostics, Coralville, IA) using the local anatomical properties of the airways and the pulmonary vessels. Fissures surfaces obtained from these probabilities were then corrected by trained analysts. For more details, please refer to the study by Gerard et al. [1]

[1] Gerard, Sarah E., et al. "FissureNet: a deep learning approach for pulmonary fissure detection in CT images." *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 38.1 (2018): 156-166.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All image data will undergo a uniform pre-processing pipeline before being released to participants:

- Anonymization and format: Any DICOM metadata identifying patients or sites will be removed. Images will likely be converted to NIFTI or MHA format for convenience (a single 3D volume per file), or provided as DICOM without identifying tags. We will ensure that both scans of a pair have the same orientation and coordinate system.

- Resampling: We will resample all CT volumes to a consistent voxel size, probably 1.0 mm × 1.0 mm × 1.0 mm isotropic. COPDGene scans have sub-millimeter spacing in-plane and up to 2.5 mm between some slices for expiration; resampling ensures a common grid for all images and avoids giving advantage to methods tuned to a specific resolution. The interpolation for resampling will be trilinear for intensity values (the images are scalar fields). We expect minimal quality loss since most data is high-res; for lower-res expirations, interpolation will smooth slightly but not significantly affect registration difficulty (if anything, it might help methods by making resolution uniform).

- Cropping/registration (affine): We will apply a global affine alignment between each inspiration-expiration pair to

remove any gross differences due to patient positioning. Specifically, we plan to perform an initial rigid or affine registration of the expiration scan to the inspiration scan for each case (for example, align based on maximizing overlap of lung masks or aligning the spine). This will eliminate any trivial translations or rotations. The resulting affine-transformed expiration image will be the one provided as “moving image” to participants (or we will provide the affine matrix so participants know how images are initially positioned). By doing this, we shift the focus to deformable differences rather than allowing a method to gain extra points just by finding a big translation. If we find that the majority of cases are already well-aligned (since same-session scans often align well inherently), we might skip explicit affine registration and simply rely on the scanner coordinates (which typically align the two scans in the DICOM space using the table location). Regardless, we will ensure that when a participant loads a pair of images, they overlap reasonably (the lungs occupy similar regions in space), so no one has to handle huge initial displacements.

- Intensity normalization: CT intensities are in Hounsfield Units (HU). We will clip CT values to the interval [-1024, 1024] HU to remove outliers and rescale image intensities to -1 and 1.

- Output format and consistency: All images after preprocessing will have the same voxel dimensions and resolution, allowing easy feeding into networks. The coordinate origin for both images in a pair will coincide (so that a zero deformation means they line up as given). Participants will get the images after these preprocessing steps, so they won't need to perform them. This standardization aims to simplify the challenge for participants so they can focus on deformable registration logic rather than handling different spacings or misalignments. We will document the preprocessing steps on the website so everyone knows exactly what was done to the data. Notably, these steps are identical for training, validation, and test sets. If any additional preprocessing is done for the test set (unlikely, except the same steps as above), it will be the same as what was done for training.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Since our “ground truth” is based on automatic segmentation rather than manual, one source of error is the inaccuracy of these segmentations. For instance, in case of fissure segmentation, FissureNet achieved a high area under the precision-recall curve (PRAUC) of 0.98. However, it could still struggle in some challenging cases where manual intervention and inspection will be practiced.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Beyond annotation accuracy, another challenge is the lack of a direct ground-truth deformation field. This means if two algorithms both align well, distinguishing them relies on these surrogate metrics, which might emphasize different aspects. One method might align fissures slightly better but another aligns the diaphragm better; depending on metric weighting, one could rank higher even if clinically both are similarly good. We mitigate this by using multiple metrics and a combined ranking. Additionally, differences in lung content between scans (e.g., mucus plugs or transient airway closure) could cause areas that don't truly correspond. For example, an airway might be open in inspiration but closed in expiration (thus visible in one scan and not the other). Even a perfect registration can't align a structure that only exists in one image. This could affect intensity-based assumptions but our metrics (fissure, lobe, surface) are chosen such that they focus on structures present in both scans. (A closed airway doesn't affect lung surface or fissure positions.) So while such physiological changes are a source of

registration difficulty, they are not exactly an “evaluation error” – they are part of the problem definition.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will employ several complementary metrics to evaluate the registration results, reflecting the multi-faceted goals of accuracy and plausibility:

1. Lobar Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC): After applying a participant’s deformation field to the moving (expiratory) image, we will also warp the lobe segmentation masks of the moving image to the fixed image space. For each of the five lung lobes, we will compute the Dice similarity coefficient between the warped moving lobe and the corresponding lobe in the fixed image. These per-lobe DSCs will then be averaged (possibly weighted by lobe volume) to yield an overall lobar alignment score. A higher DSC (closer to 1) indicates better overlap, hence better registration. Lobar DSC primarily assesses region-level accuracy – the alignment of large anatomical regions of the lung.
2. Fissure overlap PRAUC: We will specifically evaluate how well the pulmonary fissures align. The fissure is essentially the boundary between lobes. We will compute the PRAUC between the warped fissure mask from the moving scan and the fissure mask of the fixed scan.
3. Lung boundary overlap: This metric assesses how well the overall lung surfaces are aligned. We will warp the whole-lung mask of the moving image to the fixed image and compute the Dice similarity with the fixed image’s lung mask. This yields the overlap of the outer lung contours. Additionally, we will compute a surface distance-based metric, such as the average or 95th-percentile Hausdorff distance (HD95) between the two lung surfaces after registration, to gauge boundary alignment in distance terms. However, the primary reported metric will be lung mask Dice since it’s simple and robust. Lung boundary alignment reflects the global shape alignment of the lungs – important for ensuring no large gaps or slips (for instance, if one lung apex is not aligned, Dice will drop).
4. Diaphragm Surface Distance: For each lung (left and right), we will identify the costophrenic angle (the lowest lateral point of the lung) of the moving and fixed image. From that, we will compute the average symmetric surface distance (ASSD) to measure alignment quality.
5. Transformation regularity metrics: To assess the physical plausibility of the deformation, we will calculate the percentage of voxels with non-invertible mapping, commonly measured by the fraction of the volume where the Jacobian determinant of the deformation is non-positive (≤ 0). This is often termed the “folding percentage.” A lower percentage (closer to 0%) is better, indicating an almost diffeomorphic transform. We will report the percent of voxels with Jacobian ≤ 0 in the warped moving image.

6. Runtime: We will measure the wall-clock time each algorithm takes to register one case (and/or all cases, averaged). This will be done by timing the Docker container on a standard hardware setup for the full test set and dividing by number of cases (if run sequentially). We will also note memory usage if relevant (since extremely heavy memory requirements could be impractical). Runtime will be expressed in seconds (or minutes) per case. While not a direct accuracy metric, this is an important practical metric. We will include it as a factor in a secondary ranking or simply report it for information.

Each of the above metrics maps to the challenge aims: metrics 1–4 measure accuracy (with 1 and 3 being volumetric overlaps, 2 focusing on thin structures, 4 giving point-wise error), metric 5 measures plausibility/regularity, metric 6 addresses reliability/robustness, and 7 addresses efficiency.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

- The Dice coefficient for lobes and lungs is a standard overlap measure widely used in medical image segmentation and registration evaluation. A high Dice means the structures overlap very well.

- The fissure overlap metric (PRAUC) is chosen because fissures make up a small fraction of the total voxels within the lung and reporting Dice may not be appropriate.

- The costophrenic angle alignment (ASSD over the diaphragm) will measure distance between the aligned diaphragm surfaces to assess alignment quality.

- The non-diffeomorphic volume percentage (folding) is crucial for evaluating if the algorithm's output is physically meaningful. In real anatomy, the lungs do not fold through themselves; a registration that creates fold-overs implies either numerical instability or unrealistic mapping.

- Finally, runtime is included because in real-world biomedical applications, time is often limited.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The challenge will use a multi-metric ranking scheme inspired by the Medical Segmentation Decathlon and Learn2Reg challenges. For each metric listed above, we will rank the participating methods. However, rather than simply averaging raw metric values (which have different scales and importances), we will convert each metric result into a normalized rank score. The procedure is as follows: for a given metric (say, mean fissure PRAUC), we perform pairwise statistical comparisons between all methods to determine if differences are significant. If one method significantly outperforms another on that metric ($p < 0.05$), it is considered to "win" that comparison. We then produce a ranking of methods for that metric based on the number of wins. This yields an ordering where some methods might be statistically tied. We then map these ranks to a score between 0.1 and 1.0 for that metric (with the top method(s) getting 1.0, and the bottom method getting 0.1, for example). This approach of "significant ranking" ensures we don't over-penalize methods that are practically equivalent to each other. We will do this for each primary metric and once each method has a score for each metric, we compute an aggregate score as the

geometric mean of its metric scores.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

In the final evaluation, since we will run each algorithm's Docker on all test cases, we expect a complete set of results for each method. If a Docker submission fails to produce output for one or more test cases (e.g., due to a crash or timeout), we will handle it as follows: If the failure is minor (e.g., one case missing due to a known bug), we will assign that method the worst possible metric values for that case (essentially penalizing heavily). If a method fails on a substantial number of cases or fails to run entirely, it will be disqualified from ranking. We will communicate with teams if a container fails to try to resolve any technical issues (within reason and time constraints).

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking scheme is chosen to balance multiple objectives fairly and robustly. The geometric mean of metric scores is particularly suitable because it rewards consistency: a method that is uniformly good across all metrics will outrank a method that is excellent in one metric but poor in another.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The main statistical tool we will use is the Wilcoxon signed-rank test (non-parametric paired test) to compare methods for each metric. This test does not assume normal distribution and is appropriate for comparing two algorithms across multiple cases. For each pair of methods A and B, we will test the null hypothesis that there is no difference in their performance distribution (e.g., Dice differences have zero median). A two-sided p value less than 0.05 will be considered to be significantly different.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

To quantify the precision of each evaluation metric, we will compute 95% confidence intervals using nonparametric bootstrapping. Specifically, we will approximate the sampling distribution of each metric by repeatedly resampling the observed cases with replacement and recomputing the metric. The 95% confidence interval will then be derived from the empirical distribution of the bootstrap estimates, for example using percentile or bias-corrected and accelerated (BCa) intervals.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

We will assess performance variability across test cases using summary statistics such as the mean, standard deviation, and interquartile range (IQR). Variability will be visualized using boxplots and distribution plots to highlight dispersion and potential outliers.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

We will assess ranking variability by analyzing how algorithm ranks change across resampled test cases. This will allow us to perform pairwise comparisons across all methods using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test and rank

methods based on the number of statistically significant wins, allowing score sharing in the presence of ties. To ensure robust comparisons we will use bootstrapping for repeated sampling.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is standard paired comparisons since it accounts for the paired nature of results (each algorithm produces one result per case, so methods can be compared case-by-case). It's more appropriate than an unpaired test since the same cases are used by all methods, reducing variance. We choose a non-parametric test because metric distributions (especially Dice or TRE differences) might not be normal, and because performance data often have outliers or are bounded.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Missing data are not expected during the final test phase. All participating methods are submitted as Docker containers and executed by the organizers on every test case, ensuring complete and consistent result generation across all submissions.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

We will use software like pandas and numpy for data handling, SciPy or statsmodels for tests, and potentially scikit-learn or custom scripts for any additional analyses.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Further analyses: In addition to the primary evaluation, we plan a number of supplementary analyses and experiments to glean more insight from the challenge:

Baseline algorithms and upper-bound estimation: We will run several existing registration algorithms on the challenge data as baselines. These will include classic non-learning methods like ANTs (Symmetric Normalization), the original Lucas-Kanade Demons algorithm, and perhaps Elastix or NiftyReg, which are commonly used for lung image registration. We will also test modern learning-based methods, for example VoxelMorph (unsupervised CNN registration) and a transformer-based method similar to TransMorph. These baseline results will be released to participants (perhaps on the validation set) so they know what performance to beat. Additionally, we will evaluate a trivial baseline: the identity transform (no registration) – which essentially shows the initial misalignment metrics. This is important to quantify how much improvement each method provides over doing nothing; for instance, identity will have some baseline lung overlap and some large diaphragm error, etc. By comparing methods to identity, we can compute registration improvement percentages.

Baselines:

To reiterate, planned baseline methods include:

- VoxelMorph (unsupervised CNN, MICCAI 2018 & TMI 2019) – we'll train it on our data to have a reference

learning method.

- TransMorph (MedIA 2022) – a recent transformer-based registration network, to see if it improves over CNN baseline.
- ANTs SyN (the diffeomorphic SyN algorithm, well-known classical approach).
- NiftyReg or Elastix (B-spline) – a parametric spline-based classic method.
- DEEDS (Discrete Dense Registration) – a fast discrete optimization method that has been successful in lung CT in literature.
- Demons (Thirion's algorithm) – perhaps with modifications like symmetric forces, as a representative optical flow method.

Finally, we note that the challenge remains open after MICCAI, so we will keep analyzing any new submissions that come in, updating the community if new best methods appear (like how EMPIRE10 remained open for years). This helps the benchmark stay relevant.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A